

1 Minimal Liquid Discharge System for Sustainable Dairy 2 Wastewater Management

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10 Graphical Abstract

11

12 Abstract

13 The dairy industry is a significant producer of wastewater, contributing to the deterioration of both the
14 quality and quantity of freshwater resources. Moreover, the high daily and seasonal variability in the
15 composition and volume of dairy wastewater poses challenges for efficient recycling. Minimal Liquid
16 Discharge (MLD) systems, capable of achieving water recovery rates of up to 95%, have attracted
17 increasing attention from both scientific and industrial sectors. However, their technological complexity,
18 high energy requirements, and the challenge of managing produced concentrate remain significant
19 barriers to broader industrial adoption. In this study, an MLD system comprising microfiltration, reverse
20 osmosis, and an agitated vacuum evaporator was designed and experimentally evaluated. Additionally,
21 the biogas yield potential of the produced sludge was assessed to explore sustainable concentrate
22 management strategies. At a water recovery rate of 89.8%, the treated effluent exhibited COD, BOD,
23 and TDS values of 66 mg/L, 55 mg/L, and 134 mg/L, respectively, indicating strong potential for reuse
24 as rinsing and cleaning water for non-food surfaces or as cooling water. A biogas yield of 32.3 Nm³/t_{FM}
25 demonstrates that the sludge could be a viable co-substrate for anaerobic digestion in biogas plants.
26 Furthermore, the techno-economical assessment revealed that, for optimized water recovery rates, the
27 payback period can be as short as 2.8 years, underscoring the economic viability of this approach. Future
28 development will focus on system optimization, long-term operation tests to better understand the
29 system behavior, and economic sensitivity analysis to investigate the impact of various factors.

30 **Keywords:** reverse osmosis, microfiltration, vacuum evaporation, biogas, recycling, concentrate
31 valorization

32 **Highlights:**

- 33 • A water recovery of 89.8% was achieved using a Minimal Liquid Discharge system.
- 34 • Recycled wastewater can be used for cleaning or cooling processes.
- 35 • A biogas yield of 32.3 Nm³/t_{FM} was obtained from the produced sludge.
- 36 • The payback period for the proposed technology can be as short as 2.8 years.

37 **1 Introduction**

38 Freshwater scarcity is an increasing global concern, driven by population growth, urbanization, and
39 industrial expansion as well as the impacts of global climate change [1]. Wastewater production further
40 exacerbates this issue by deteriorating both the quality and quantity of freshwater sources. In Europe,
41 industries generate approximately 54% of all wastewater [2]. Wastewater recycling presents a promising
42 solution to mitigate the impact of industrial activities on water scarcity. It enables the reuse of water
43 within industrial plants, conserving freshwater resources and reducing the overall demand for
44 freshwater. Additionally, it promotes environmental sustainability by minimizing wastewater discharge
45 into the environment and alleviating pressure on natural water bodies.

46 The dairy industry stands out as one of the most water-intensive among the industrial sectors. A
47 significant portion of water used in dairy plants is discharged as wastewater. According to the Best
48 Available Techniques (BAT) document for the milk industry [3], the production of 1 L of milk results
49 in generating 0.3–10 L of wastewater from the plant. Stasinakis et al. [4] estimated that dairy plants in
50 EU-27 countries generate 192.5 million m³ of wastewater annually. The majority of this wastewater
51 comes from plant cleaning and process operations (heating and cooling), accounting for approximately
52 49% and 42%, respectively [5]. Cleaning procedures, which may be performed regularly up to several
53 times a day, involve washing floors, cleaning tanks, milk silos, milk transport lines, and other equipment.
54 These operations introduce different sanitizers and detergents, such as sodium hydroxide, sodium
55 carbonate, nitric and phosphoric acid solutions, and other chemicals, contributing to the pollution of
56 wastewater with these chemicals [6].

57 The main pollutants in dairy wastewater (DWW) are the milk constituents and other milk products, such
58 as milk proteins, fats, lipids, and carbohydrates. This results in a high organic load, characterized by
59 high chemical oxygen demand (COD) and biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) levels reaching up to
60 13,000 mg/L and 11,100 mg/L, respectively [4]. Additionally, dairy wastewater contains suspended and
61 dissolved solids, chlorides, sulphates, trace organics, fats, and nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus
62 compounds.

63 The volume and composition of DWW vary on a daily and seasonal basis, due to the batch nature of
64 many dairy processes and periodic operations, such as cleaning and sanitizing [4]. Additionally, milk
65 production is highly seasonal, and the wastewater characteristics (volume and composition) of DWW
66 depend on the type of final product. According to the BAT document for the milk industry [3],
67 wastewater generation ranges from 1.9–17.2 m³ per tonne of raw material for fermented milk production
68 and from 0.24–4.9 m³ per tonne of raw material for cheese production. The significant variation in dairy
69 effluent composition is summarized in Table 1, based on data from the studies of Stasinakis et al. [4],
70 Bella and Rao [6], and Slavov [7]. For instance, the reported COD values vary widely: cheese effluent
71 ranged from 785–63,300 mg/L, whey processing effluent from 1,070–2,180 mg/L, ice cream effluent
72 from 4,935–10,418 mg/L, and mixed dairy effluent between 500–13,060 mg/L. These variations
73 highlight the diversity in organic pollution levels associated with different dairy processing activities.

Dairy effluents	pH	COD	BOD	TSS	TN	TP
Dairy wastewater	3–11	500–13,060	240–11,100	60–9,625	10–660	5–600
Whey processing effluent	4–9	1 070–102,100	590–60,000	80–22,150	200–2,000	120–640
Cheese processing effluent	3–11.3	785–63,300	565–5,722	190–3,560	18–830	5–280
Ice cream wastewater	4.2–9.8	4,935–10,418	2450	1,043–3,100	60–165 (TKN)	14–43
Yogurt, butter, and buttermilk processing effluent	4,5–12	2,000–10,000	220–2,650	700–5,070	40–60	–

75 The variability in DWW volume and quality presents a significant challenge for effective treatment.
 76 Currently, DWW is typically pretreated at dairy plants before being discharged into municipal sewage
 77 systems. Traditional DWW treatment methods include various aerobic and anaerobic processes,
 78 coagulation/flocculation, and flotation [8]. However, these methods are usually not capable of reducing
 79 pollution to levels suitable for water reuse. To overcome these limitations, numerous studies have
 80 explored the implementation of advanced technologies such as membrane processes [5]. Additionally,
 81 innovative treatment frameworks like Zero Liquid Discharge (ZLD) and Minimal Liquid Discharge
 82 (MLD) are also gaining attention for their ability to achieve high water recovery rates and enhance the
 83 sustainability of wastewater management practices [9,10].

84 The fundamental principle of ZLD is the complete recycling of wastewater, ensuring that no liquid
 85 effluent is discharged from the industrial plant into the environment or sewage system. Additionally,
 86 valuable substances are recovered from the wastewater and either reused or commercialized. However,
 87 these requirements significantly increase costs, energy consumption, and system complexity.
 88 Consequently, the MLD concept has gained significant attention in recent years due to its lower capital
 89 costs and energy demands compared to ZLD [11]. MLD aims to minimize wastewater production while
 90 maximizing the recovery of valuable substances [12], achieving water recovery rates as high as 95%
 91 [11]. A typical ZLD/MLD system incorporates membrane processes such as nanofiltration (NF),
 92 ultrafiltration (UF), and reverse osmosis (RO), as well as thermal processes such as evaporators (multi-
 93 stage flash distillation or multi-effect distillation), brine concentrator, brine crystallizer or evaporation
 94 ponds [10]. Emerging technologies such as forward osmosis, membrane distillation, electrodialysis,
 95 eutectic freeze crystallization, and humidification-dehumidification are also being extensively
 96 researched and gradually implemented at the pilot scale [10,13].

97 More and more studies have been conducted to deal with DWW recycling, particularly focusing on
 98 membrane processes. Garnier et al. [5] reviewed pressure-driven membrane processes used in various
 99 food industries, highlighting NF and RO as the primary recycling technologies for dairy wastewater.
 100 Other review studies on food and dairy wastewater treatment also mentioned microfiltration (MF) and
 101 UF as possible recycling technologies [14–16]. According to Brião et al. [17] recycled dairy rinse
 102 wastewater treated with RO can be used as feed water for cooling towers or boilers, and potentially for
 103 second and third flush during clean-in-place (CIP). However, the permeate quality does not meet
 104 drinking water standards, which require a total organic carbon (TOC) level below 5 mg/L. The authors
 105 also suggested that the milk solids from retentate could be recovered and added to dairy products.
 106 Vourch et al. [18] achieved high-quality RO permeate, with TOC below 2.1 mg/L and electrical
 107 conductivity (EC) of 3 mg/L, which is comparable to vapor condensate quality. This water could be
 108 reused for heating, cooling, or cleaning water in dairy plants. The successful recycling of low-pollutant

109 dairy condensates from flash coolers using RO was investigated by Suárez et al., and Suárez and Riera
110 [19,20]. Additionally, Bortoluzzi et al. [21] compared MF + NF and MF + RO membrane systems for
111 treating raw dairy wastewater. Their results showed that the MF + RO system achieved reductions of
112 100% in turbidity and color, 94% in total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), and 84% in TOC. It is concluded
113 that this treated water can be reused in cooling and heating processes.

114 Vacuum evaporation (VE) is a well-established separation method that has been widely used for decades
115 in various industrial sectors to separate volatile components from solutions, suspensions, and emulsions
116 [22]. Vacuum evaporation presents several important advantages, such as robust operation, high
117 recovery rate, no need for supplementary materials, and the ability to treat a wide range of liquid
118 mixtures [23], including the stage of crystallization (in crystallization evaporators). Consequently, it is
119 gaining importance in wastewater treatment, particularly for sludges and other waste suspensions. Xu et
120 al. [24] proposed evaporation and cooling crystallization as part of the ZLD technology for the
121 desulfurization wastewater treatment. Si et al. [25] experimentally investigated a mechanical vapor
122 recompression evaporation system coupled with membrane distillation to treat industrial wastewater
123 with high sodium chloride content. The main drawback of VE is its high energy consumption, which
124 can range from about 28 kWh per cubic meter of separated water (distillate) in multi-stage evaporators
125 with mechanical vapor recompression to nearly 740 kWh/m³ in the simplest single-effect evaporators
126 with external heat source [26]. For integrating VE into an MLD system, it is advisable to minimize the
127 volume of the wastewater treated by VE or to optimize this volume with respect to the overall economic
128 feasibility of the technical design.

129 Currently, VE is widely used in the dairy industry for the concentrating milk, whey, and other milk by-
130 products [27], typically followed by spray drying to produce milk powders [28,29]. However, its
131 application for dairy wastewater treatment remains uncommon. Altieri et al. [30] investigated the use of
132 a vacuum evaporator for treating highly polluted raw whey wastewater from a cheese-making plant,
133 reporting mean removal efficiencies of 96.1% for EC, 98.9% for BOD, 99.3% for COD, and 98.9% for
134 total nitrogen (TN). Despite these high removal efficiencies, the final distillate quality was unsuitable
135 for reuse in the dairy plant, as COD and BOD concentrations exceeded 600 mg/L and 300 mg/L,
136 respectively. The application of VE to salty dairy wastewater originating from whey demineralization,
137 CIP processes, and chromatography wastes was briefly mentioned in a review by Chen et al. [31].
138 However, no additional studies specifically addressing vacuum evaporation for dairy wastewater
139 treatment have been identified in the existing scientific literature.

140 In recent years, resource recovery from wastewater has gained increasing attention as a key aspect of
141 the circular economy and sustainable development. DWW represents a valuable source of secondary
142 raw materials, offering the potential to recover a variety of co-products. For instance, bioethanol can be
143 produced through the fermentation of lactose present in DWW by strains of the yeast *Kluyveromyces*
144 [32]. A study by Leandro et al. [33] demonstrated efficient lactose conversion from reverse osmosis
145 retentate into bioethanol, achieving yields exceeding 90%. Furthermore, lipids extracted from DWW
146 sludge can be converted into biodiesel [34], or the sludge can serve as a growth medium for different
147 types of bacteria strains [35]. Additionally, valuable compounds such as proteins, lipids, biopolymers,
148 and organic acids can be recovered [15,16,36], further highlighting DWW's potential as a versatile
149 resource within the circular economy framework.

150 Biogas, a clean and sustainable energy source, is a valuable by-product of DWW processing, offering
151 significant potential to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and lower greenhouse gas emissions. Anaerobic
152 digestion of organic waste, including DWW sludge, plays a key role in this process. Kunatsa and Xia
153 [37] emphasized the importance of further research on optimizing co-substrate ratios, addressing
154 seasonal variations in substrate availability, and improving the efficiency of anaerobic co-digestion.
155 Sembera et al. [38] demonstrated that using dairy and food waste as co-digestates can significantly
156 enhance biogas yield. Their study identified waste milk, lactose, and grease trap sludge as the most
157 profitable co-substrates, further underscoring the potential of integrating DWW sludge into biogas

158 production systems. Moreover, sludge from anaerobic digestion of DWW can serve as a potential
159 biofertilizer due to its high content of essential nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus, primarily in the
160 form of struvite [39].

161 As aforementioned, the scientific literature has recognized the potential of DWW recycling via
162 membrane processes. However, the subsequent treatment or disposal of retentate is often overlooked in
163 these studies. Additionally, although vacuum evaporation is a well-established wastewater treatment
164 process, its application to DWW remains insufficiently investigated in the literature. Research indicates
165 that DWW sludge could be an effective substrate for co-digestion in biogas plants. In this study, it is
166 important to note that the term *concentrate* refers to the final product of evaporation, which may also
167 contain a significant amount of suspended solids. In wastewater treatment contexts, such a product is
168 also commonly referred to as sludge. Therefore, the terms *concentrate* and *sludge* are used
169 interchangeably in this study.

170 This study presents a novel MLD system designed to address the challenges of dairy wastewater
171 recycling by integrating membrane and thermal processes to maximize water recovery, while
172 incorporating anaerobic digestion for sustainable sludge management. The system comprises
173 microfiltration, reverse osmosis, agitated vacuum evaporation, and anaerobic digestion. The aim of the
174 proposed system is to produce high-quality water suitable for reuse within the dairy plant while
175 simultaneously generating energy from the sludge through biogas production.

176 The main objective of this study is to experimentally assess the performance of the proposed MLD
177 system for dairy wastewater treatment. The evaluation focuses on the quality of treated water and its
178 potential for reuse, as well as the biogas yield potential of the produced concentrate. A secondary
179 objective is to conduct a techno-economic assessment based on a case study of a medium-sized dairy
180 plant to evaluate the feasibility of the system at an industrial scale. Based on the case study, the MLD
181 system is further optimized to identify the most economically viable configuration.

182 **2 Methodology**

183 **2.1 Experimental Setup**

184 The proposed MLD system integrates MF, RO, an agitated vacuum evaporator (AGEV), and anaerobic
185 digestion. A schematic representation of the experimental setup is provided in Figure 1.

186

187

Figure 1 Scheme of the experimental setup

188 The treatment process began with feed wastewater being processed through the MF unit. The MF
 189 permeate was then fed into the RO unit, while the retentates from both the MF and RO units were
 190 collected, homogenized, and processed using the AGEV. All the membrane processes (MF, RO) were
 191 operated in batch mode, where retentate was recirculated into the feed tank and gradually concentrated,
 192 and permeate was collected in a separate tank. The AGEV was operated in a semi-batch mode. The
 193 initial volume of wastewater was introduced into the pressure vessel, and once the evaporation reached
 194 a target level, another feed wastewater was added. This approach enables the increase of the water
 195 recovery rate.

196 Samples of the AGEV concentrate, feed wastewater, and retentates from the RO and MF units were
 197 subjected to anaerobic digestion in the laboratory to access biogas yield potential. Additionally, all
 198 samples were analyzed for their chemical composition in an external laboratory. Details of the chemical
 199 analysis and fermentation testing methods are described in Section 2.6. This system was designed to
 200 achieve high water recycling efficiency while simultaneously managing the concentrated solution and
 201 recovering energy in the form of biogas.

202 2.2 Feed Wastewater Characteristics

203 Raw dairy wastewater used in the experiment was provided by a Czech dairy plant, comprising a mixture
 204 of the various effluents from the plant, including grey water and black water. The wastewater was stored
 205 in a refrigerator at 4°C to prevent biological processes from altering its properties and was used within
 206 three days of collection. Table 2 summarized the wastewater characteristics, including pH, EC, COD,
 207 BOD, total suspended solids (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS), ammonium nitrogen (NH₄-N), TN,
 208 and total phosphorus (TP).

Table 2 Feed wastewater characteristics

Parameter	Value	Unit
pH	4.7 ± 0.2	–
EC	2 970 ± 119	µS/cm
COD	3 920 ± 392	mg/L
BOD	2 670 ± 534	mg/L
TSS	2 040 ± 245	mg/L
TDS	1 910 ± 229	mg/L
NH ₄ -N	6.9 ± 0.7	mg/L
TN	79.3 ± 15.8	mg/L
TP	24.4 ± 2.9	mg/L

210 *Note: ±denotes measurement uncertainty

211 2.3 Apparatuses

212 The experimental apparatuses include a microfiltration, a reverse osmosis system, and an agitated
 213 vacuum evaporator. The MF membrane was a tubular design with 8 channels, a mean pore size of 1.4 µm,
 214 and an active membrane area of 0.2 m². The membrane is made of TiO₂ and manufactured by Tami
 215 Industries. The RO apparatus consists of two modules with spiral wound polyamide thin film composite
 216 membrane (RE2521-BE) from CSM company. The manufacturer reported NaCl rejection rate is 99.7%,
 217 and the active membrane area is 1.1 m². The RO modules were connected in series so that the retentate
 218 from the first module serves as the feed for the second module. A centrifugal pump (Calpeda TP100/B)
 219 with a frequency speed converter was used for all membrane units. A plate and frame heat exchanger
 220 was used to regulate the feed wastewater temperature for all the membrane units.

221 The in-house made AGEV unit consists of a pressure vessel (35 L of active volume) with double shell,
 222 an agitator with frequency converter and inclined blades, a demister and a plate condenser (SWEP
 223 B80SHx20/1P-SPS-M), a membrane pump (Seaflo SFDPA2-030-045-33) for distillate removal and a
 224 vacuum system (centrifugal pump Calpeda MXHM 206 and two vacuum ejectors) with a maximum
 225 vacuum level of 0.04 bar_A. The heat source is hot water (up to 90 °C) from an electric boiler. The
 226 maximum distillate production is approximately 10 L/h.

227 The experimental apparatuses also contain instrumentation for pressure, temperature, and volume flow
 228 rate measurement. All sensors were supplied by the IFM company. Pressures were measured with PN
 229 2594, PM 1605, PM 1609, PM 1504, and PM 1103 sensors. Volume flow rates and temperatures were
 230 measured with SM 6020, SM 7020, and SM 8020 sensors. Piping and Instrumentation diagram of all
 231 experimental units is provided in Annex A.

232 2.4 Operating Conditions

233 The experiments for individual technologies were conducted over four consecutive days. The total
 234 amount of treated DWW was 162 L. The wastewater was stored in a refrigerator at 4°C before and
 235 between experiments. The operating conditions were selected based on the pump's operational
 236 limitations and the optimal parameters specified by the membrane manufacturer. The average operating
 237 parameters for membrane processes and evaporation are summarized in Table 3. The temperature of the
 238 wastewater fluctuated within ±5°C of the mean temperature (see Table 3).

Treatment stage	Operating parameters		
	Trans membrane pressure (TMP) [bar]	Feed volume flow rate [L/min]	Temperature [°C]
MF	4.0	45.5	27.3
RO (M1)	12.7	14.6	27.3
RO (M2)	12.4	13.9	
	Chamber pressure [bar _A]		Temperature [°C]
AGEV	0.08		34.0

240 *Note: M1 and M2 denote membrane 1 and membrane 2 for reverse osmosis unit

241 The removal efficiency (E_R , %) for different compounds was calculated according to Eq. (2.1). Where
242 C_P (mg/L) and C_F (mg/L) are the concentrations in the permeate and the feed.

$$E_R = \left(1 - \frac{C_P}{C_F}\right) \cdot 100 \quad (2.1)$$

243 The recycled water yield is determined in terms of the water recovery (R , %) given by the ratio (2.2) of
244 the permeate volume (V_P , m³) and the feed volume (V_F , m³).

$$R = \frac{V_P}{V_F} \cdot 100 \quad (2.2)$$

245

246 The performance of the membranes was evaluated using the normalized water flux (J_W , L/m²h)
247 calculated according to Eq. (2.3), where Q_P (L/h) is the permeate volume flow rate, A (m²) is the active
248 area of the membranes, and T (°C) is the temperature. To eliminate the influence of temperature on flux
249 measurements, a correction factor was applied. The chosen referenced temperature is 25 °C.

$$J_W = \frac{Q_P}{A} \cdot 1.03^{(25-T)} \quad (2.3)$$

250

251 The normalized hydraulic permeability (L_P , L/m²h.bar) was given as a ratio (2.4) of the normalized water
252 flux and the trans-membrane pressure (TMP, bar).

$$L_P = \frac{J_W}{TMP} \quad (2.4)$$

253

254 The performance of the vacuum evaporator was determined in terms of the distillate volume flow rate
255 (Q_{dist} , L/h), which was calculated according to Eq. (2.5), where V_{dist} (L) is the volume of produced
256 distillate and t (h) is the duration of evaporation.

$$Q_{dist} = \frac{V_{dist}}{t} \quad (2.5)$$

257

258 The specific heat energy consumption ($SEC_{heat,AGEV}$, kWh/m³) of the vacuum evaporator is determined
259 according to Eq. (2.6) as the ratio of mean heat power input ($P_{heat,AGEV}$, kWh) to distillate volume flow
260 rate. Similarly, the specific electrical consumption ($SEC_{el,AGEV}$, kWh/m³) was determined with Eq. (2.7),
261 where $P_{el,AGEV}$ (kWh) denotes the mean electrical power input.

$$SEC_{heat,AGEV} = \frac{P_{heat,AGEV}}{Q_{dist}} \cdot 1000 \quad (2.6)$$

$$SEC_{el,AGEV} = \frac{P_{el,AGEV}}{Q_{dist}} \cdot 1000 \quad (2.7)$$

263 2.5 Cleaning of Membranes

264 Each membrane was soaked in a preservative solution to prevent microbial growth. The MF membrane
 265 was stored in a 0.5% (v/v) H₂O₂ solution, while the RO membranes were stored in a solution of 1 %
 266 w/w sodium bisulfite (SBS) solution. Prior to each experiment, the membranes were flushed with
 267 potable water for 30 minutes to ensure the complete removal of any residual chemicals from the
 268 preservative solution. After each experiment, the membranes were cleaned with a 1% (w/w) NaOH
 269 solution (RO) or a 1.5% (w/w) NaOH solution (MF) for 30 minutes. Subsequently, the membranes were
 270 flushed with potable water for an additional 30 minutes. Before and following each experiment, the
 271 AGEV was thoroughly cleaned with potable water for 45 minutes. Additionally, backflushing with
 272 potable water was performed every 30 to 50 minutes during microfiltration to reduce fouling and
 273 enhance the water flux. The backflush lasted usually between 1 to 2 minutes.

274 2.6 Characterization of Physicochemical Parameters and Biogas 275 Production

276 The chemical parameters of the effluents were analyzed in an external accredited laboratory following
 277 Czech technical standard (ČSN) procedures. The analytical methods for each parameter were as follows:
 278 BOD₅ was determined according to ČSN EN ISO 5815-1 [40] and ČSN EN 1899-2 [41]; non-dissolved
 279 substances according to ČSN EN 872 [42]; dissolved substances according to ČSN 75 7346 [43]; total
 280 phosphorus according to ČSN EN ISO 6878 [44]; total nitrogen according to ČSN EN ISO 11905-1
 281 [45]; ammonium nitrogen according to ČSN EN ISO 11732 [46], and chemical oxygen demand
 282 according to ČSN ISO 6060 [47].

283 The pH value and the electrical conductivity were measured *in situ* during sampling using a WTW
 284 ProfiLine Multi 3320 meter equipped with SenTix 21 and TetraCon 325 electrodes. Biogas production
 285 was determined following the standard procedure described in VDI 4630 [48]. The biogas yield was
 286 expressed as normal cubic meters of biogas per tonne of fresh matter (FM). Fermentation tests were
 287 performed with inoculated samples with activated anaerobic sludge at the temperature of 41–42°C, with
 288 continuous monitoring of biogas production and composition.

289 2.7 Techno-economic Assessment Assumptions

290 The techno-economic assessment is based on a predictive model that quantifies the economic savings,
 291 capital expenditures (CAPEX), and operating costs for a given design. The decision variables that define
 292 a design point are the water recoveries in each of the three process steps (MF, RO, AGEV). The
 293 assessment can facilitate optimization and Scenario comparison.

294 In this case study, the assumed wastewater capacity of the dairy plant is 100 m³/d, corresponding to a
 295 medium-sized dairy plant. The process parameters (Table 4) used in this case study are derived from
 296 experimental results conducted in this study (see Section 3.3). The feed pressure values are set based on
 297 the measurements obtained in the experiment. The water flux values measured at the end of the
 298 experiments are used. These values represent the final water recovery, i.e. concentration polarization
 299 and fouling exert the highest influence, thereby ensuring a conservative approach that avoids
 300 overestimating membrane performance.

301 *Table 4 Process parameters for membrane processes used in techno-economical assessment*

Process parameter	MF	RO
Feed pressure [barg]	4.2	12.9
Water flux [L/m²h]	45	18

302 The mass balance is calculated based on recoveries, which define the fractions of the feed stream to the
 303 given process unit that exits as permeate (membrane) and distillate (evaporator).

304 For membrane processes, the following workflow and cost functions are used. The active membrane
 305 area is calculated from Equation (2.8) with the temperature correction omitted. The cost functions of
 306 membrane processes are assumed to be linearly dependent on the active membrane area. To account for
 307 scale effects on cost estimation, a 0.9 exponent was used instead of the 1.0 standard exponent. This
 308 adjustment reflects the economies of scale - the specific CAPEX cost decreases as the system scales up
 309 from the relatively small scale presented in this case study. The cost function is formulated as:

$$C_{mem,i} = a_i \cdot A_i^{0.9} \quad (2.8)$$

310 where $C_{mem,i}$ (EUR) is the equipment cost of a membrane i , which is either MF or RO. a_i (EUR) and
 311 A_i (m²) are the calculation coefficient and active area of each membrane. The coefficients were
 312 determined based on a known cost at a given reference area and are summarized in Table 5. The
 313 corresponding unit cost at the reference point is considered conservative, at 31.5 EUR/m² for RO and
 314 151.9 EUR/m² for MF.

315 *Table 5 Overview of purchased equipment cost for membrane processes.*

Membrane process	a_i (EUR)	Reference cost (EUR)	Reference area (m ²)	Source	Note
MF	223.9	7353.1	48.4	[49] (p. 483)	A lower bound for ultrafiltration, assumed CEPCI = 800
RO	45.2	1171.3	37.2	[50]	Incl. VAT

316 *CEPCI = Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index

317 The pump power ($P_{pump,i}$, kW) corresponding to the membrane process i (RO or MF) is calculated (2.9)
 318 as follows [51]:

$$P_{pump,i} = 0.0275 \cdot \frac{Q_{P,i} \cdot P_{feed,i}}{R_i \cdot \eta} \quad (2.9)$$

319 where $Q_{P,i}$ (m³/h) is the permeate flow, $P_{feed,i}$ (barg) is the feed pressure, R_i is the recovery rate (–) of
 320 the membrane process i , η (–) is the pump efficiency and is assumed as 0.7. The pump cost function
 321 $C_{pump,i}$ is considered linear and based on Czech pump market research, with a factor of 520 EUR/kW
 322 shaft work.

323 For the agitated vacuum evaporator, mechanical vapor compression (MVC) is assumed as the most
 324 energy-efficient approach for larger scales [26]. The real cost of turnkey MVC evaporators is obtained
 325 from a Czech vendor and used to develop the following cost estimation in EUR (2.10):

$$C_{AGEV} = 354,502 \cdot Q_{dis}^{0.5} \quad (2.10)$$

326 where Q_{dis} (m³/h) is the produced distillate flow rate. To estimate the total capital investment, ratio
 327 factors based on delivered-equipment cost presented in an existing study [52] are used with the following
 328 minor adjustments:

- 329 • Only direct costs are included.
- 330 • Yard improvements are excluded due to the small spatial foot of the technology.
- 331 • The service facilities factor is reduced from 70% to 20 % as many standard utilities and services
- 332 (e.g., steam generation, compressed air systems, fuel supply, refrigeration, waste management,
- 333 etc.) are not required for this process.
- 334 • The instrumentation and control factor for RO is doubled considering the process control
- 335 complexity and the need for high-pressure-resistant sensors.
- 336 • Cost elements already included in the turnkey evaporator cost (such as installation,
- 337 instrumentation and control, and piping) are not duplicated.

338 The parameters are summarized in Table 6.

339 *Table 6 Summary of purchased equipment scope and ratio factors based on delivered-equipment cost.*

	MF	RO	AGEV
Purchased Equipment (PE) includes	Membrane modules and pump	Membrane modules and pump	Self-contained evaporator
Installation	47 % of PE		47 % of PE
Instrumentation and control	36 % of PE	72 % of PE	Included in PE
Piping	68 % of PE		Included in PE
Electrical systems	11 % of PE		Included in PE
Building modifications	18 % of PE		18 % of PE
Service facilities (esp. storage)	20 % of PE		20 % of PE
CAPEX Subtotal	3 · PE	3.36 · PE	1.85 · PE

340 The total capital investment (CAPEX in EUR) is calculated (2.11) as:

$$CAPEX_{tot} = 3(C_{mem, MF} + C_{pump, MF}) + 3.36(C_{mem, RO} + C_{pump, RO}) + 1.85C_{AGEV} \quad (2.11)$$

341 Operating expenditures (OPEX) are assumed to consist of three major contributors:

- 342 • energy cost – calculated via power demand (RO and MF) or specific energy consumption (a
- 343 large-scale one-stage MVC evaporator), and electricity cost in Czechia in H1 2023 (the most
- 344 conservative value over the last 5 years);
- 345 • chemicals cost – considered proportional to the permeate or distillate flow rate of a specific unit,
- 346 • maintenance cost – as a percentage of PE costs; for MF and RO, this corresponds to an assumed
- 347 total replacement frequency of membranes and pumps (every 2 years for MF, every 3 years for
- 348 RO).

349 In addition, the annual operating time is assumed as 8000 hours including maintenance and other shut-

350 down periods. The parameters for OPEX calculations are presented in Table 7.

351 Table 7 Parameters used for OPEX calculations.

	MF	RO	AGEV
Power demand	Equation (2.9)		40 kWh/m ³ distillate [26]
Electricity cost	0,2 EUR/ kWh [53]		
Specific chemicals cost	0,025 EUR/m ³ [54]		
Specific maintenance cost	50 % PE/y	33 % PE/y	2 % PE/y

352 The following equations (2.12)–(2.15) is used to determine the total operating expenses:

$$OPEX_{el} = \left(\sum_{i \in \{MF, RO\}} P_{pump,i} + Q_{dis} \cdot SEC_{AGEV} \right) c_{el} AOT \quad (2.12)$$

353

$$OPEX_{chem} = \left(\sum_{i \in \{MF, RO\}} Q_{P,i} + Q_{dis} \right) c_{chem} AOT \quad (2.13)$$

354

$$OPEX_{maint} = 0.5(C_{mem, MF} + C_{pump, MF}) + 0.33(C_{mem, RO} + C_{pump, RO}) + 0.02C_{AGEV} \quad (2.14)$$

355

$$OPEX_{tot} = OPEX_{el} + OPEX_{chem} + OPEX_{maint} \quad (2.15)$$

356 where $OPEX_{el}$, $OPEX_{chem}$, $OPEX_{maint}$, and $OPEX_{tot}$ (EUR/y) are the annual energy, chemicals,
 357 maintenance, and total operating costs. SEC_{AGEV} (kWh/m³) is the specific energy consumption of AGEV
 358 related to the distillate production, c_{el} represents the unit electricity cost (EUR/kWh), AOT (h) is the
 359 annual operating time, c_{chem} (EUR/m³) is the specific chemical cost associated with permeate
 360 production (for membrane) or distillate production (for evaporator operation).

361 As a counterpart to the presented technology costs, the economic benefits are categorized into three
 362 types of savings: (a) wastewater treatment savings, (b) sludge management savings, and (c) water
 363 savings.

364 Wastewater treatment savings are estimated at 1.5 EUR/m³. This is based on a biological treatment
 365 operational cost of 1.21 EUR/m³ reported by Stasinakis et al. [4] for a large dairy processing plant. This
 366 value is further increased by approximately 25% to account for the annualized capital investment
 367 required for the proposed treatment technology.

368 The savings in sludge management are based on two key factors. Firstly, the sludge from the proposed
 369 MLD technology preserves the organic matter, which increases its value for biogas production.
 370 Secondly, the technology is able to reduce the sludge volume compared to biological treatment. Based
 371 on real dairy processing plant data from Slovakia, biological treatment can convert 13% of the initial

372 wastewater volume into sludge. In a case study [55], the sludge management costs were estimated at
373 40 EUR/m³, which is a conservative value for on-site composting. Alternative treatments like external
374 composting and thermal treatment are significantly more expensive – by 45% and 88 %,
375 respectively [55].

376 The model takes into account the effect of the increased value of the sludge produced by the MLD
377 technology. This trend of reduced (or even negative) gate fees at anaerobic treatment plants, driven by
378 higher biogas yield, has also been reported by other authors [38]. A conservative estimation assumes a
379 50% reduction of sludge management cost, resulting in a cost of 20 EUR/m³, and the final concentrate
380 is less than 10% of the original wastewater volume. For concentrates between 10% and 20%, sludge
381 management costs increase linearly from 20 EUR/m³ to 40 EUR/m³. If the concentrate exceeds 20%,
382 the preserved organic content becomes too diluted, diminishing the biogas production benefits, and the
383 sludge is no longer considered valuable.

384 Water reuse savings are the third type of cost reduction in the assessment. These savings are based on
385 the unit water cost in Czechia, which ranges from 3.4 and 4.6 EUR/m³ [56]. A mid-range value of
386 4 EUR/m³ is used for the calculations. It is assumed that 20% of the produced water volume is used for
387 backflushing of the membranes, while 40% does not meet the quality requirements and cannot fully
388 replace drinking water. Thus, a conservative estimate assumes that the remaining 40% contributes to
389 cost savings.

390 The overall savings are therefore calculated as in (2.16):

$$S_{a_{tot}} = AOT(Q_{feed}c_{treat} + Q_{con}c_{sludge} + Q_{wat}c_{wat}) \quad (2.16)$$

391 where $S_{a_{tot}}$ (EUR/y) are the annual savings, Q_{feed} , Q_{con} and Q_{wat} (m³/d) are the feed, concentrate,
392 and water flow rates, c_{treat} , c_{sludge} and c_{wat} (EUR/m³) are the specific savings for wastewater
393 treatment, sludge management, and water reuse.

394 The main basis to evaluate and optimize different Scenarios is the payback period PP (y) calculated as
395 follows (2.17):

$$PP = \frac{CAPEX_{tot}}{S_{a_{tot}} - OPEX_{tot}} \quad (2.17)$$

396 In this study, four Scenarios are considered for the techno-economic assessment, and the last three are
397 optimized to achieve the lowest payback period.

- 398 • Scenario A – MF + RO + AGEV (the base case): the recovery ratios were observed in the real-
399 world laboratory experiment.
- 400 • Scenario B – MF + RO + AGEV: the recovery ratios are manipulated parameters in the
401 optimization, and the values are constrained to 0–90%. The minimum distillate production is
402 constrained to 0.25 m³/h to maintain a reasonable MVC evaporator scale.
- 403 • Scenario C – MF + RO: the recovery ratios for membrane processes are constrained identically
404 to Scenario B, whereas the AGEV’s recovery ratio is set as 0.
- 405 • Scenario D – MF + RO + AGEV with distillate polishing: the constraints are identical to
406 Scenario B. “Distillate polishing” refers to a modified process configuration where distillate is
407 mixed with RO feed to improve the final water quality.

408 3 Results Analysis

409 3.1 Water Quality

410 The quality of wastewater streams treated by the MLD system is summarized in Table 8, while the
411 removal efficiencies of the individual technologies are illustrated in Figure 2. The MF process

412 substantially reduced the suspended solids in the wastewater to 6 mg/L with a removal rate of 99.7%.
 413 Additionally, visual inspection confirmed that the MF permeate was colorless, as shown in Figure 3.
 414 For other quality parameters such as COD, BOD, and TN, the reduction was less significant, and
 415 removal efficiencies ranged from 3% (TN) to 66% (COD). These results align with the expectations, as
 416 the primary function of MF is to remove the suspended solids from the wastewater prior to the RO step,
 417 thereby minimizing membrane fouling.

418 *Table 8 The physicochemical characteristics of treated wastewater streams*

Wastewater stream	Parameters								
	pH [-]	EC [μ S/cm]	COD [mg/L]	BOD [mg/L]	TSS [mg/L]	TDS [mg/L]	NH ₄ -N [mg/L]	TN [mg/L]	TP [mg/L]
MF permeate	4.8 \pm 0.01	1 351 \pm 56	1 340 \pm 134	1 130 \pm 226	6 \pm 0.7	1 850 \pm 222	3.4 \pm 0.34	42.5 \pm 8.5	19.9 \pm 2.4
MF retentate	4.2 \pm 0.01	1 408 \pm 56	6 880 \pm 688	3 640 \pm 728	2 110 \pm 253	2 010 \pm 241	7.2 \pm 0.72	90.8 \pm 18.1	26.6 \pm 3.2
RO permeate	5.2 \pm 0.01	99 \pm 4	66 \pm 7	55 \pm 11	<2 \pm 0.2	134 \pm 16	0.5 \pm 0.05	4.8 \pm 1	<0.03 \pm 0.003
RO retentate	4.7 \pm 0.01	5 950 \pm 238	6 090 \pm 609	4 080 \pm 816	224 \pm 27	9 040 \pm 1085	18.1 \pm 1.8	210.0 \pm 42	98.9 \pm 11.9
AGEV distillate	3.7 \pm 0.01	117 \pm 5	162 \pm 16	159 \pm 32	<2 \pm 0.2	210 \pm 25	0.2 \pm 0.02	3.7 \pm 0.7	<0.03 \pm 0.003
AGEV concentrate	4.4 \pm 0.01	11 570 \pm 463	80 800 \pm 8 800	35 700 \pm 7140	28 400 \pm 3408	19 400 \pm 3408	82.8 \pm 2328	748.0 \pm 149	315 \pm 37.8

419 *Note: \pm denotes measurement uncertainty

420
 421 *Figure 2 Removal efficiencies of individual treatment technologies; AGEV* related to feed wastewater*

422 Using ceramic membranes from the same manufacturer, Zielińska and Galik [57] reported similar
 423 removal efficiencies for suspended solids (turbidity removal >99%) but higher COD removal
 424 (approximately 89%) with an average permeate COD concentration of 175 mg/L. They attributed this
 425 to the particle adsorption inside the membrane, which enhanced the removal of organic substances by
 426 MF [57]. On the other hand, Bortoluzzi et al. [21], who used polymeric (PES/PVP) hollow fiber
 427 membranes, observed low removal efficiencies of 82% for color, 78% for turbidity, 0–6% for COD, 5–

428 17% for TKN, and 0–9% for TOC. A more recent study [58] reported high removal efficiencies of
429 suspended solids (color 95.8%, turbidity 83.7%) and organic pollutions (COD 47.5%; permeate
430 concentration ~ 1 900 mg/L). However, the results are still lower than those obtained in the present study
431 and those reported in Zielińska and Galik [57], suggesting that ceramic membranes may represent a
432 more suitable option for dairy wastewater treatment.

433

434 *Figure 3 Photography of samples of the feed wastewater (A), MF retentate (B), and MF permeate (C)*

435 As shown in Figure 4, the RO process exhibited high removal efficiencies, ranging from 84% to 100%.
436 Specifically, COD and BOD were reduced by 95.0% and 95.1%, resulting in final concentrations of
437 66 mg/L and 55 mg/L, respectively. In contrast, lower removal efficiencies of 84% and 88.6% were
438 observed for TN and NH₄-N, though the final concentrations in the permeate remained low (0.5 mg/L
439 for NH₄-N and 4.8 mg/L for TN). Furthermore, TDS and EC were reduced by 92.8% and 92.6%, yielding
440 final values of 134 mg/L and 99 μ S/cm, respectively. These results indicate that the RO process
441 effectively rejects organic matter and salts with relatively good efficiency. Although the final
442 contamination levels are relatively low, they do not meet drinking water quality standards. Nevertheless,
443 the recovered water still has the potential to be reused for cleaning and rinsing operations, which will
444 be discussed in more detail in Section 3.2.

445 Literature comparisons further highlight variations in RO efficiency. Vourch et al. [18] reported removal
446 efficiencies for TOC, EC, and TKN of 99.9% (final permeate concentration of 2 mg/L), 97.8% (final
447 permeate concentration of 17 μ S/cm), and 96.3%, respectively, for dairy wastewater treatment by RO.
448 In contrast, Bortoluzzi et al. [21], using raw dairy wastewater with MF pretreatment, observed lower
449 reductions in TOC (82.5%) and TKN (92.3%), resulting in TOC permeate concentration of 138 mg/L
450 and TKN permeate concentrations of 3 mg/L. In the study by Brião et al. [17], the permeate COD and
451 EC levels were 88 mg/L and 95 μ S/cm, respectively. Suárez et al. [19] reported that RO EC removal
452 efficiencies ranged from 70.3% to 93.7%, depending on the type of feed wastewater (dairy condensates
453 from rinsing vs. production steps) and given operating temperature. The EC permeate concentrations
454 varied between 20 μ S/cm and 60 μ S/cm. The COD removal efficiency was 100% for dairy condensates
455 from rinsing and 65%–78% for dairy condensates from production steps. The final COD permeate
456 concentrations varied between 10 mg/L and 25 mg/L.

457

458 *Figure 4 Photography of samples of RO retentate (A), RO permeate (B), AGEV distillate (C) and AGEV concentrate (D)*

459 The literature review highlighted significant variability in RO and MF removal efficiencies across
 460 different studies. This variation underscores the dependence of performance on feed wastewater
 461 characteristics, operating conditions, and membrane material and type. It also suggests that the proper
 462 design of this technology for dairy wastewater treatment is a complex process. Therefore, pilot testing
 463 is essential for tailoring the system design to specific industrial applications.

464 The distillate from AGEV exhibited higher contamination levels than the RO permeate (see Table 8).
 465 The COD, BOD, and EC levels in the distillate were 162 mg/L, 159 mg/L, and 117 μ S/cm, respectively.
 466 Additionally, the distillate had a lower pH of 3.7, indicating the presence of volatile organic compounds,
 467 such as low molecular weight organic acids (e.g., acetic, lactic, formic, and propionic acids). These
 468 compounds contribute to the elevated COD and the acidity, and are likely by-products of milk and dairy
 469 residue decomposition [59]. The relatively low EC (117 μ S/cm) compared to the TDS (210 mg/L),
 470 suggests that the distillate primarily contains weakly ionizing organic compounds rather than inorganic
 471 salts, which could theoretically enter through micro-droplet entrainment. The TN content of 3.7 mg/L
 472 further supports minimal nitrogenous compounds transfer into the distillate. These findings suggest that
 473 while the evaporation process effectively separates non-volatile and high-molecular-weight
 474 components, it allows the carryover of volatile organic compounds, which can impact the quality and
 475 potential reuse of the recovered water.

476 The removal efficiencies for most parameters exceeded 90% (see Figure 2). However, it is important to
 477 note that these values reflect the quality of the feed wastewater to the entire MLD system rather than the
 478 actual wastewater entering AGEV unit. This distinction arises due to the lack of specific wastewater
 479 quality data for AGEV unit. Consequently, the actual AGEV removal efficiencies are likely higher than
 480 the reported values. The elevated contamination levels in the distillate limit its reuse potential, and
 481 without additional treatment, it is unsuitable for recycling within the plant. Further discussion on this
 482 issue is provided in Section 3.2.

483 The concentrate from the evaporator exhibited extremely high pollution levels, as expected (Figure 4).
 484 High concentrations of organic pollution as well as suspended and dissolved solids are observed. The
 485 measured concentrations of COD, BOD, TDS, and TSS were 80,800 mg/L, 35,700 mg/L, 28,400 mg/L,
 486 and 19,400 mg/L, respectively. Such highly contaminated effluent requires proper disposal, which could
 487 pose a significant financial burden for dairy processors. To address this challenge, an additional

488 treatment step for this effluent in our MLD system – anaerobic digestion – is proposed to reduce costs
 489 and enhanced resource recovery (see Section 3.4).

490 3.2 Recycled Water Utilization

491 Water quality is a critical factor in determining its potential for reuse. First, the quality of RO permeate
 492 is evaluated. This water does not meet drinking water quality standards [60,61], and cannot be used for
 493 cleaning and rinsing surfaces that come into direct contact with dairy products. However, it could be
 494 potentially suitable for cleaning and rinsing other non-food surfaces, such as floors, outdoor areas, dairy
 495 trucks, and the external surfaces of equipment and apparatuses.

496 In the Czech Republic, there are no general quality standards for recycled industrial wastewater. Instead,
 497 specific quality standards and permissible uses are determined on a case-by-case basis by the Regional
 498 Hygiene Authority. When comparing the characteristics of the permeate with Czech standards for dairy
 499 wastewater discharges into water bodies [62], most parameters were compliant, except for pH and BOD
 500 (see Table 9). Nevertheless, pH variations are generally not a concern for cleaning and rinsing
 501 operations, as pH is usually significantly altered by the use of alkaline or acidic cleaning agents, such
 502 as sodium hydroxide and various acids. The BOD limit for discharge is 30 mg/L, while the BOD in this
 503 study was reduced to 55 mg/L. While this difference should not pose significant issues for non-food
 504 surface cleaning, particularly when cleaning agents are used, the final determination of suitability
 505 remains the responsibility of the Regional Hygiene Authority.

506 *Table 9 Comparison of RO permeate and EU and Czech water quality standard*

Standards	Water quality parameters							
	pH [-]	EC [μS/cm]	COD [mg/L]	BOD [mg/L]	TSS [mg/L]	NH ₄ -N [mg/L]	TN [mg/L]	TP [mg/L]
RO permeate	5.2	99	66	55	<2	0.5	4.8	<0.03
Discharge to water bodies according to Czech legislative [62]	6–8.5		120	30	50	10	30	5
Drinking water quality according to Czech legislative [60]	6.5–9.5	1 250	3	–	–	0.5	–	–
Drinking water quality according to EU legislative [61]	6.5–9.5	2 500	–	–	–	0.5	–	–
Water quality for industrial cooling systems according to ČSN 75 7171 [63]	6–9.5	1 200*; 2 000*; 3 500*	50	–	15*; 20*; 50*	0*; 3*; 8*	–	–
Water quality for agricultural irrigation according to EU Regulation 2020/741 [64]	–	–	125	25	35	–	–	–
Water quality for treated wastewater use for irrigation projects according to ČSN ISO 16075-2 [65]	A	–	–	60	90	–	–	–
	B	–	–	20	30	–	–	–

507 *Maximum values vary depending on the construction materials used. A–limited irrigation of industrial crops and
 508 seed crops; B–agricultural irrigation of non-food crops

509 Brião et al. [17] examined the potential use of recycled water in CIP systems for flushing or rinsing
 510 between alkaline and acid cleaning steps. Due to a higher residual COD of 88 mg/L, they concluded it

511 was unsuitable for such applications. Given that the permeate COD in this study is 66 mg/L, we concur
512 with their assessment that this water is unsuitable for CIP applications.

513 Another potential application for RO permeate is its use in cooling towers. Cooling tower water must
514 have low concentrations of suspended solids, organic pollutants, and dissolved salts, as well as a pH
515 range of 6-9.5 [63]. The permeate has a pH value below the recommended range, which requires
516 adjustment to minimize the risk of corrosion and scaling. Furthermore, the slightly elevated levels of
517 organic contamination may increase the risk of biological fouling in the cooling systems, which could
518 be controlled through the addition of biocide solutions [66].

519 RO permeate could also be used for irrigating seed crops, where the permissible BOD limit is 60 mg/L
520 [65]. This presents a viable opportunity for dairy plants engaged in cattle breeding, as recycled
521 wastewater could be used for fodder irrigation, enhancing water resource efficiency and contributing to
522 a more circular water management approach.

523 In comparison, the distillate has lower usability than RO permeate due to its higher COD and BOD
524 values, as well as its lower pH, which is not favorable for many applications. However, additional
525 treatment with RO (see Figure 5) could improve its usability. If the distillate stream were fed into the
526 RO system, its composition would be significantly enhanced, simultaneously diluting the feed water
527 entering the RO stage, reducing the pollution load, and improving the quality of the RO permeate.
528 Nevertheless, pH adjustment would remain necessary. Another option is to adjust the pH of the
529 wastewater (retentate) before evaporation. Increasing the pH would increase the dissociation of the
530 organic acids present and thus reduce the transfer of these pollutants into the distillate.

531

532 *Figure 5 The scheme of the proposed configuration to enhance recycled water quality*

533 Furthermore, another option to reduce permeate contamination is to apply a second pass through the RO
534 system. Vouch et al. [18] demonstrated that the TOC levels can be reduced to below 2.1 mg/L using
535 this approach. Brião et al. [17] reported a COD reduction of only 52%, resulting in a final COD
536 concentration of 42 mg/L after the second pass through the RO membrane. Nevertheless, even with such

537 a low reduction of organic pollution, the permeate COD could be reduced below 50 mg/L, and the BOD
 538 potentially below 30 mg/L, thereby meeting both cooling water and discharge water standards.

539 Another option for increasing wastewater reusability involves separating individual wastewater streams
 540 prior to treatment. For example, separating grey and black water from cleaning and rinsing water could
 541 reduce pollutant loads and contaminant variability, thereby improving treatment efficiency and permeate
 542 quality. This stream-specific approach can enhance the overall performance of the treatment process and
 543 result in better-quality treated water. According to the BAT document [3], dairy plants have the potential
 544 to recycle cleaning solutions, final rinses from CIP processes, and vapor condensates, either directly or
 545 after advanced treatment, especially if these streams are kept separate. Such recycled water could be
 546 used for cleaning external surfaces of equipment and vehicles, for CIP pre-rinse, or even as the main
 547 cleaning water supply in CIP systems. Implementing these measures would enhance water circularity
 548 within the plant and contribute to fresh water savings.

549 It is important to note that evaluating the potential application of recycled wastewater in practice should
 550 also include monitoring of additional parameters, such as heavy metals and microbiological indicators
 551 including *E. coli* and *Legionella spp.* Although these indicators were not measured in this study, the RO
 552 permeate exhibits promising potential for reuse in non-critical cleaning applications, cooling tower
 553 operation (with pH adjustment and biocide dosing), and seed crop irrigation. In contrast, the distillate is
 554 less suitable for reuse due to its elevated organic contamination. However, its quality could be improved
 555 either by directing it into the reverse osmosis system or by adjusting the pH of the retentate prior to
 556 evaporation. Separating wastewater streams and introducing a second pass through the RO membrane
 557 offers promising opportunities to improve the treated water quality and broaden its potential reuse
 558 applications.

559 3.3 Technology Performance

560 The performance parameters are summarized in Table 10. The water recovery achieved during the MF
 561 stage was approximately 58%, with a mean normalized water flux of about 64 L/m²h. As mentioned
 562 earlier, backflush with potable water was performed during MF to mitigate membrane fouling. The
 563 results showed a rapid initial decline in water flux (from 200 L/m²h to 50-60 L/m²h) at the start of the
 564 individual rinsing cycles, followed by a stabilization at a lower level over time (see Figure 6). The
 565 variability around the mean values is depicted in the form of 5-minute interval box plots. Overall, a
 566 gradual decline in water flux was observed throughout the experiment, evidenced by the decreasing peak
 567 values and stabilized levels over consecutive cycles. At a water recovery of 58%, the normalized water
 568 flux stabilized at approximately 45 L/m²h (indicated by the red dotted line in Figure 6). This decline can
 569 be attributed to substantial fouling and concentration polarization resulting from the progressive
 570 accumulation of suspended solids and organic substances (fats, oils, proteins, lactose) in the feed
 571 wastewater.

572 *Table 10 An overview of performance data for individual treatment stages*

Treatment stage	Performance parameters					
	R [%]	J _w [L/m ² h]	L _p [L/m ² h.bar]	Q _{dist} [L/h]	SEC _{heat,AGEV} [kWh/m ³]	SEC _{el,AGEV} [kWh/m ³]
<i>MF</i>	58.1	64.2	16.35	–	–	–
<i>RO</i>	85.2	25.0	1.99	–	–	–
<i>AGEV</i>	80.1	–	–	6.26	692.6	179.0
<i>MLD system</i>	89.8					

573 The water flux achieved in this study exceeds the values reported by Zielińska and Galik [57]. In their
 574 study, a ceramic membrane from the same manufacturer is used, and feed wastewater with comparable
 575 characteristics is investigated, resulting in a water flux of 12.5 L/m²h. In terms of hydraulic

576 permeabilities, which account for pressure normalization, Zielińska and Galik [57] reported an average
 577 value of 8.3 L/m²h.bar, whereas the present study achieved 16.35 L/m²h.bar. This substantial difference
 578 can be primarily attributed to the smaller pore size of the membrane used in their study (0.45 μm vs.
 579 1.4 μm in this study). On the other hand, Bortoluzzi et al. [21] and Bortoluzzi et al. [58] reported higher
 580 hydraulic permeabilities for the hollow fiber polymeric membrane (polyether sulfonate/polyvinyl
 581 pyrrolidone) with a pore size of 0.2 μm, ranging from 31.7 to 63.4 L/m²h.bar. These results suggest that
 582 polymeric MF membranes may offer a more efficient and economically viable alternative for dairy
 583 wastewater treatment when compared to ceramic membranes. However, it is important to note that the
 584 recommended flow rate from the membrane manufacturer (approx. 70 to 80 L/min) was not achieved
 585 during the experiment conducted in this study. The available pump was unable to deliver the required
 586 flow rate at the desired operating pressure. Achieving a higher flow rate could potentially mitigate the
 587 effects of concentration polarization and fouling, thereby enhancing water flux.

588
 589 *Figure 6 The box plot of normalized permeate flux for MF during the experiment*

590 For the RO stage, the achieved water recovery was approximately 85%, with a mean normalized water
 591 flux of 25 L/m²h, corresponding to hydraulic permeability of approximately 2 L/m²h.bar. During the
 592 experiment, the water flux gradually declined from over 30 L/m²h to 18 L/m²h as water recovery
 593 increased (Figure 7). Figure 7 also shows fluctuations around the mean permeate flux using 5-minute
 594 interval box plots. These results are comparable to, or exceed, those values reported in the literature for
 595 dairy wastewater. Vourch et al. [18] reported water flux values of 11–13 L/m²h (with hydraulic
 596 permeability 0.55–0.65 L/m²h.bar) at a water recovery of 90%. Bortoluzzi et al. [21] documented water
 597 flux of 14 L/m²h at 30 bar and 7 L/m²h at 20 bar after 60 min of operation. Brião et al. [17] achieved a
 598 water flux of 20 L/m²h at 20 bar and 15 °C for a water recovery of about 90%.

599

600 *Figure 7 The box plot of normalized permeate flux for RO during the experiment*

601 The observed decrease in permeate flux with increasing recovery is consistent with the findings of all
 602 aforementioned studies. This trend can be attributed to concentration polarization [17], which occurs
 603 when solutes accumulate near the membrane surface, forming a concentration gradient that reduces
 604 driving force and hinders water transport. Additionally, the formation of a gel layer [18,21] caused by
 605 the deposition of retained particles (such as milk proteins, polysaccharides, and amino acids) further
 606 intensifies this effect by introducing an additional resistance to flow, thereby reducing membrane
 607 permeability. A similar fouling mechanism was observed during the MF stage, where pore blocking
 608 caused by suspended solids was the main reason [57]. The permeate flux is an important parameter from
 609 an economic point of view; therefore, fouling plays a crucial role in the design of membrane technology.
 610 Although the results of this study indicate promising performance, careful evaluation and optimization
 611 of operational parameters and final water recovery remain essential to ensure the long-term technical
 612 and economic feasibility at an industrial scale.

613 The mean distillate volume flow rate was about 6.3 L/h. The distillate production was deliberately set
 614 lower than the AGEV output allows (up to 10 L/h) to reduce the risk of foaming in the concentrated
 615 wastewater (retentates) and to minimize the entrainment of microdroplets into the distillate. The
 616 resulting recovery rate of the AGEV was 80.1%. This result was achieved with a specific heat
 617 consumption of 693 kWh/m³, which corresponds to the normal consumption of single-stage evaporators
 618 with an external heat source [26]. In single-stage evaporation, specific heat consumption is
 619 predominantly determined by the latent heat of vaporization of water. In contrast, the specific electric
 620 consumption observed in this study was 179 kWh/m³, which exceeds the industrial standards. This is
 621 because the individual electrical appliances on the AGEV unit (agitator, pumps) are oversized and not
 622 optimized for industrial use. In terms of the operation of the agitated evaporator, no complications were
 623 observed during the experiments.

624 In this study, the MLD system achieved a total water recovery of approximately 90% (see Figure 8).
 625 This performance closely aligns with the theoretical recovery targets of the MLD concept, which can
 626 reach up to 95% [11]. However, determining the optimal total water recovery for industrial-scale
 627 applications requires a detailed techno-economic evaluation tailored to the specific conditions and
 628 operational constraints of individual dairy plants. Furthermore, the water recovery rates of individual
 629 treatment technologies should be adapted to accommodate site-specific factors, including wastewater
 630 composition and volume. The design of such integrated systems inherently involves multiple degrees of
 631 freedom, making optimization and practical implementation particularly challenging.

632

633 *Figure 8 The scheme of the experiment with final material balance*

634 **3.4 Biogas Yield**

635 A critical issue limiting the industrial application of these technologies is the disposal of concentrate
 636 from recycling technology. This waste stream is typically regarded as a highly polluted by-product that
 637 requires costly disposal by industrial plants. To address this issue and support the MLD approach, this
 638 study investigated the potential use of dairy wastewater concentrates as a co-digestion substrate in biogas
 639 plants. One of the primary objectives of this study was to evaluate biogas yield from individual
 640 concentrate/retentate streams to determine their optimal usability.

641 The results (Table 11) demonstrated that the biogas yield from the MF retentate ($3.3 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{t}_{\text{FM}}$) and RO
 642 retentate ($2.9 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{t}_{\text{FM}}$) was relatively low – only marginally higher than the biogas yield from feed
 643 wastewater ($2.5 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{t}_{\text{FM}}$). This indicates that, under the tested conditions, the MF and RO waste streams
 644 are not economically viable for co-digestion in biogas plants. Moreover, their low total solids content is
 645 suboptimal for anaerobic digestion, further limiting their utilization as a biogas plant substrate. In
 646 contrast, the concentrate obtained from vacuum evaporation exhibited a biogas yield of $32.3 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{t}_{\text{FM}}$,
 647 with a methane content of approximately 59%. This performance is comparable to the biogas yield
 648 reported for cattle and pig manure ($20\text{--}35 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{t}_{\text{FM}}$) [67,68], which are commonly utilized substrates in
 649 biogas plants. Additionally, the total solids content in the concentrate (5.6%) confirms its suitability as
 650 a substrate for biogas production. The measured methane content aligns well with typical biogas
 651 methane concentrations, which range from 55% to 70% [69,70]. Thus, the caloric value of biogas
 652 produced from vacuum evaporation concentrate is expected to be comparable to the caloric value of
 653 conventional biogas.

654 It is important to emphasize the inherent dependency between water recovery and biogas yield. Higher
 655 water recovery increases the concentration of nutrients (carbohydrates, proteins, fats) in the substrate,
 656 which are essential for biogas production potential. Therefore, it can be assumed that increasing the
 657 water recovery rate of MF and RO processes would improve the biogas yield of their respective retentate,
 658 potentially enhancing their economic value as biogas substrates. However, achieving a 90% water

659 recovery rate in the MLD system without vacuum evaporation requires high water recovery rates of at
 660 least 95% for both MF and RO processes. This would significantly increase operational and capital costs
 661 and intensify the risk of membrane fouling, which could pose significant operational challenges.

662 The findings from this section highlight the potential value of dairy wastewater concentrate from
 663 vacuum evaporation as a valuable substrate for biogas production. This approach offers an
 664 environmentally sustainable disposal method while enabling energy recovery, thereby offsetting part of
 665 the technological energy demand. Additionally, biogas plant operators could incentivize nearby dairies
 666 by offering financial benefits, such as discounts on sludge disposal fees or direct compensation for dairy
 667 plant sludge.

668 Conversely, the results reveal that the retentates from MF and RO stages ("sludge") at the given water
 669 recovery rates are not economically attractive for co-digestion in biogas plants. While increasing water
 670 recovery rates for these processes could potentially improve the economic viability of the retentate, this
 671 would simultaneously increase the overall costs of the technologies. These insights are crucial for the
 672 future design and optimization of MLD systems in the dairy sector.

673 *Table 11 Anaerobic digestion performance of different DWW streams.*

Treatment stage	Biogas yield* [Nm ³ /t _{FM}]	Dry matter in biogas feedstock [%]	CH ₄ content* [%]
<i>Feed</i>	2.5±0.15	0.34	63.2±0.37
<i>MF</i>	3.3±0.20	0.31	62.7±0.29
<i>RO</i>	2.9±0.21	0.9	58.7±1.68
<i>AGEV</i>	32.3±1.57	5.62	59.2±0.51

674 *Note: ±denotes standard deviation from 3 measurements

675 **3.5 Techno-economic Assessment**

676 The results of the techno-economic assessment are presented in Figure 9, which compares the techno-
 677 economic assessment results of the four Scenarios. The primary comparative parameter in this
 678 assessment is the payback period (PP). Additionally, annual net savings are estimated, representing the
 679 difference between total annual savings and total operational expenditures for each scenario. The height
 680 of each PP element corresponds to one year and is proportional to the height of the annual net savings
 681 column, providing a geometric representation of the equation (2.17).

682

683 *Figure 9 The results of techno-economic assessment including CAPEX, OPEX, savings, annual net savings, and PP for*
 684 *Scenarios A to D*

685 In the base case (Scenario A), which reflects the water recovery rates achieved in the experiments, the
 686 PP was calculated as 11.5 years. This extended payback period was attributed to the high CAPEX and
 687 OPEX costs associated with the vacuum evaporator, which required a high processing capacity to meet
 688 system demands. To mitigate these challenges, water recoveries for individual technologies were
 689 optimized to decrease the total costs and shorten the payback period.

690 In the optimized configuration (Scenario B), the water recovery rates for MF and RO were set to 90%,
 691 representing the upper limit defined for the optimization algorithm. Additionally, the total MLD water
 692 recovery of 90% proved to be the most economically favorable. Consequently, the water recovery rate
 693 for AGEV was reduced to approximately 47%, substantially lowering its capacity. This reduction led to
 694 a substantial decrease in total CAPEX, which fell to 458,300 EUR, approximately 50% lower than the
 695 CAPEX in Scenario A (889,100 EUR). Similarly, the OPEX was reduced to 41,900 EUR, representing
 696 only one-third of the OPEX (126,400 EUR) in Scenario A. Consequently, the PP was shortened to 2.82
 697 years, demonstrating promising economic returns for potential implementations in dairy plants. These
 698 results suggest that the optimized system could be economically competitive on an industrial scale.

699 Given the high costs of the vacuum evaporator, an alternative configuration excluding this technology
 700 was evaluated in Scenario C. In this scenario, the water recovery rates for MF and RO were also set to
 701 90%. As a result, both the OPEX (13,500 EUR) and CAPEX (56,700 EUR) were considerably lower.
 702 However, the total savings were also reduced, leading to a higher PP of 4.57 years. The lower savings
 703 were primarily due to negative sludge savings, as the absence of the vacuum evaporator led to higher
 704 sludge volumes (19% of the feed) and reduced the biogas yield potential of the produced sludge. The
 705 sludge that is generated solely from membrane processes is less valuable to biogas plant operators,
 706 leading to higher sludge disposal costs (as discussed in Section 2.7). This relationship is also depicted
 707 in Figure 9, where the sludge savings are shown as a component of the OPEX column for Scenario C.
 708 Nevertheless, the PP of approximately 4.6 years indicates that this configuration could be economically
 709 viable in certain applications, particularly where lower technological complexity is desired. However, it
 710 should be noted that Scenario C does not fully align with the principles of the MLD strategy, thereby
 711 representing a less environmentally sustainable option.

712 Scenario D considered the treatment of distillate by the RO stage to enhance the quality of the final
713 effluent (see Section 3.2, Figure 5). The assessment was performed using optimized water recoveries
714 applied in Scenario B (i.e., MF, RO, and total recovery rates were the same as in Scenario B). Compared
715 to Scenario B, the total CAPEX (482,100 EUR) and total OPEX (45,400 EUR) in Scenario D were
716 slightly higher, resulting in a PP of approximately 3 years. These additional costs were associated with
717 the increased volume of water processed by the RO stage, which requires a larger membrane area and
718 higher pump capacity. Furthermore, the water recovery rate for the vacuum evaporator was increased
719 by 3%, slightly increasing its processing capacity and corresponding CAPEX and OPEX. However, the
720 difference in the PP between Scenario B and D is only about 2.5 months, which can be considered an
721 acceptable value given that Scenario D would achieve higher water quality. This enhancement in the
722 quality of the treated effluent makes Scenario D a highly attractive option and unlocks valuable
723 possibilities for water reuse within the plant. It should be noted, however, that these potential reuse
724 benefits were not included in the calculated water savings, as they have not yet been validated through
725 experiments, which are planned as part of future research efforts.

726 In addition to optimizing process parameters, dairy plants have the potential to utilize waste heat from
727 various thermal processes, such as ultra-high temperature processing or pasteurization. This waste heat
728 could significantly reduce energy costs for vacuum evaporation while contributing to a more
729 environmentally sustainable operation. To explore this potential, Scenario E (not included in Figure 9),
730 where waste heat is available in the dairy plant for vacuum evaporation, is analyzed. In Scenario E, a
731 multi-effect or multi-stage flash evaporator was implemented instead of an MVC evaporator. Based on
732 literature data [26], it is assumed that the power demand for vacuum evaporation would decrease from
733 40 to 14 kWh/m³ of distillate. All other assumptions remained consistent with Scenario D. As a result,
734 compared to Scenario D, the total CAPEX in Scenario E remained equal at 482,100 EUR, while the total
735 OPEX decreased to 28,000 EUR. This reduced the PP to 2.73 years, which is slightly lower than in
736 Scenario B. These findings suggest that if waste heat is available in the dairy plant, implementing a
737 thermally-driven evaporator could represent the most economically viable option. However, it should
738 be emphasized that the CAPEX was assumed to be identical to the MVC evaporator, the actual CAPEX
739 for multi-effect or multi-stage flash evaporator could vary significantly, depending on the quantity and
740 quality of the available waste heat. Lower available heat typically results in higher CAPEX due to the
741 need for more chambers and larger heat transfer surfaces, while plentiful and high-grade waste heat
742 would allow for a simpler, cheaper design. This aspect requires further investigation in future work.

743 It is important to note that increased water recovery rates for membrane processes could negatively
744 affect permeate quality, thereby reducing its reusability. Additionally, higher water recovery rates are
745 likely to intensify membrane fouling, leading to elevated maintenance costs and shorter membrane
746 lifespans. These potential trade-offs were not incorporated into the current techno-economic model,
747 which represents a limitation that may lead to a slight overestimation of economic performance in high-
748 recovery scenarios. On the other hand, the most conservative values for water fluxes (measured at the
749 end of experiments) were used in the model to avoid overestimating the membrane performance. Future
750 work will address these limitations through dedicated experiments to evaluate the impact of higher water
751 recoveries on permeate quality, fouling behavior, and overall system performance (see Section 4).

752 Overall, the techno-economic assessment demonstrated that the vacuum evaporator is the most
753 expensive apparatus in the proposed MLD system. To ensure the economic viability of the MLD system,
754 it is recommended to minimize the required capacity of AGEV through an optimized process design.
755 The results indicated that Scenario B – with optimized water recoveries – is the most economically
756 viable configuration. However, Scenario D offers a compelling alternative with higher water quality
757 with only a minor increase in costs. Additionally, if waste heat is available in the plant, switching to a
758 different evaporator type (e.g., multi-stage flash evaporator) could offer both economic and
759 environmental advantages, with heat as the main energy source instead of electricity.

4 Discussions and Future Work

The results of this study demonstrate the high potential for dairy wastewater reuse as cleaning water for non-food surfaces, make-up water for cooling towers, and irrigation water for fodder cultivation. However, the achieved water quality still presents some limitations for these applications, such as the need for biocide application and pH adjustment. To address these challenges, a new configuration for the MLD system is proposed, aiming at improving the final water quality and enhancing water reusability.

A techno-economic assessment identified vacuum evaporation as the most expensive technology within the system. Therefore, to ensure the economic viability of the MLD system, it is crucial to increase water recovery rates in the MF and RO processes. This approach would reduce the required vacuum evaporator capacity, thereby lowering associated costs. Future research will build on these findings by conducting experimental assessments to determine their influence on final water quality, system performance, and techno-economic viability.

One of the limitations identified in this study is the insufficient performance of the pump used for MF, which failed to achieve the recommended flow rate specified by the MF membrane manufacturer. Future experiments will address this issue by implementing a new properly-sized pump, which is expected to increase MF water flux and lower overall system costs. Additionally, membrane fouling in the MF and RO processes was not thoroughly assessed in the current study. Fouling remains a key challenge in membrane-based treatment systems and can negatively impact water recovery rates and operational costs. Future research should focus on long-term operational tests to better understand fouling behavior in MF and RO membranes, specifically within the context of dairy wastewater treatment. These tests could provide valuable insights for system efficiency improvements, operational cost reduction, and enhancement of long-term reliability for industrial-scale applications.

Monitoring of microbiological pollution and other harmful substances (e.g., heavy metals) in recycled water was also beyond the scope of this study. However, these indicators are crucial for evaluating potential reuse options, as most water quality standards, including those for irrigation, set limits for these parameters [64,65]. Such monitoring could enhance the usability of the recycled water or produced concentrate. For instance, digestate (a by-product of anaerobic fermentation in the biogas plant) containing concentrate derived from DWW could be used as fertilizer. However, the heavy metal content in this concentrate must be strictly controlled to ensure its safe agricultural use. Future studies should include comprehensive monitoring of these parameters to support the safe and sustainable utilization of recycled water and its by-products.

To support future design and decision-making regarding the techno-economic feasibility of the system on an industrial scale, a sensitivity analysis should be conducted. This analysis will focus on factors that vary over time or by location, such as drinking water prices, sludge disposal costs, energy expenses, wastewater composition and volume, and material costs. The sensitivity analysis aims to provide industrial partners with insights into how these parameters influence final costs and potential savings, enabling more informed investment decisions.

Additionally, future research should include a broader analysis of biogas yield. By examining a wider range of water recovery rates, it will be possible to better quantify the relationship between biogas yield and water recovery. The results would contribute to a more precise techno-economic assessment. Furthermore, verifying the efficiency of the MLD system on DWW from various dairy plants will facilitate system optimization, enhancing its robustness and reliability as a wastewater treatment technology.

An environmental assessment should also be incorporated into future work to identify potential environmental impacts and support decision-making for MLD system implementation. This will ensure a comprehensive understanding of the system's sustainability profile.

807 Finally, a long-term goal of this research is to extend the applicability of the proposed MLD system to
808 other food industry wastewaters, including those from fruit and vegetable processing, meat and fish
809 processing, sugar and starch production, as well as breweries and distilleries. These industries generate
810 substantial volumes of wastewater that may be suitable for treatment with the proposed MLD system.
811 Expanding the system's applicability to a broader range of industrial sectors will foster its development
812 and enhance its contribution to sustainable water management across various food sectors.

813 **5 Conclusions**

814 This study designed and experimentally evaluated a Minimum Liquid Discharge system incorporating
815 microfiltration, reverse osmosis, and an agitated vacuum evaporator. The biogas yield potential of the
816 resulting sludge was also assessed to identify sustainable strategies for concentrate management.
817 Furthermore, the techno-economic assessment was conducted to evaluate the feasibility of the system
818 at an industrial scale.

819 The proposed MLD system demonstrates that nearly 90% of dairy wastewater can be reused within the
820 plant for cleaning non-food surfaces, as make-up water for cooling towers, or for irrigation of fodder
821 crops, thereby reducing the potable water demand in the dairy industry. The RO permeate achieved final
822 concentrations of 66 mg/L, 55 mg/L, 134 mg/L, and 5 mg/L for COD, BOD, TDS, and TN, respectively.
823 Additionally, the produced concentrate proved to be a suitable co-substrate for biogas plants, exhibiting
824 a biogas yield of 32.3 Nm³/t_{FM}, comparable to that of cattle and pig manure. This offers a sustainable
825 and economically viable disposal route for dairy plants, addressing one of the key barriers to the
826 industrial-scale implementation of the MLD system, namely the high cost of concentrate disposal.

827 A techno-economic assessment was conducted for a dairy plant processing 100 m³ of wastewater per
828 day. The results indicated that the payback period could be less than 3 years if water recovery rates are
829 optimized to minimize the vacuum evaporator capacity. This finding is particularly relevant for potential
830 investors, as it supports further development and future large-scale implementation of the system.

831 Overall, this study provides a comprehensive assessment of the technical-economic feasibility of the
832 MLD system for dairy wastewater treatment, offering valuable insights for both industrial practitioners
833 and researchers. In addition, this work also demonstrated a viable pathway for concentrate valorization
834 through biogas production, which contributes to the concept of Circular Economy. In addition,
835 expanding the application of the proposed MLD approach to other food industries could further facilitate
836 sustainable wastewater treatment.

837 **CRedit Author Contributions**

838 **David Horňák:** Writing – Original draft, Reviewing and Editing, Conceptualization, Investigation,
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851

852 **Declaration of competing interest**

853 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that
 854 could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

855 **List of Abbreviations and Symbols**

A	Active membrane area	m ²
a	Calculation coefficient	EUR
AGEV	Agitated vacuum evaporator	
AOT	Annual operating time	
BAT	Best available techniques	
BOD	Biochemical oxygen demand	mg/L
C _{AGEV}	AGEV cost	EUR
CAPEX	Capital expenditures	
c _{chem}	Specific chemical cost	EUR/m ³
c _{el}	Specific electricity cost	EUR/kWh
CEPCI	Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index	
C _f	Feed concentration	mg/L
CIP	Clean-in-place	
C _{mem,i}	Equipment cost of a membrane	EUR
COD	Chemical oxygen demand	mg/L
C _p	Permeate concentration	mg/L
C _{pump,i}	Pump cost function	EUR/kWh
c _{sludge}	Specific savings for sludge management	EUR/m ³
ČSN	Czech technical standard	
c _{treat}	Specific savings for wastewater treatment	EUR/m ³
c _{wat}	Specific savings for water reuse	EUR/m ³
DWW	Dairy wastewater	
EC	Electrical conductivity	μS/cm
E _R	Removal efficiency	%
FM	Fresh matter	
J _w	Normalized water flux	L/m ² h
L _p	Normalized hydraulic permeability	L/m ² h.bar
M1	Membrane 1	
M2	Membrane 2	
MF	Microfiltration	
MLD	Minimal Liquid Discharge	
MVC	Mechanical vapor compression	
NF	Nanofiltration	
NH ₄ -N	Ammonium nitrogen	mg/L
OPEX	Operational expenditures	
OPEX _{chem}	Annual chemicals operating costs	EUR/y
OPEX _{el}	Annual energy operating costs	EUR/y
OPEX _{maint}	Annual maintenance operating costs	EUR/y
OPEX _{tot}	Annual total operating costs	EUR/y
PE	Purchased equipment	
P _{feed,i}	Pump feed pressure	barg
PP	Payback period	y
P _{pump,i}	Pump power	kW
Q _{con}	Concentrate flow rate	m ³ /h
Q _{dist}	Distillate volume flow rate	m ³ /h;L/h
Q _{feed}	Feed flow rate	m ³ /h
Q _p	Permeate volume flow rate	m ³ /h
Q _{wat}	Water flow rate	m ³ /h
R	Water recovery	%
RO	Reverse osmosis	
S _{atot}	Annual savings	EUR
SBS	Sodium bisulfate	
SEC _{heat,AGEV}	Specific heat energy consumption of AGEV	kWh/m ³
SEC _{el,AGEV}	Specific electrical consumption of AGEV	kWh/m ³

T	temperature	°C
t	Duration of evaporation	h
TDS	Total dissolved solids	mg/L
TKN	Total Kjehdal nitrogen	mg/L
TMP	Trans membrane pressure	bar
TN	Total nitrogen	mg/L
TOC	Total organic carbon	mg/L
TP	Total phosphorous	mg/L
TSS	Total suspended solids	mg/L
UF	Ultrafiltration	
V_{dist}	Distillate volume	L
VE	Vacuum evaporation	
V_f	Feed volume	m^3
V_p	Permeate volume	m^3
ZLD	Zero Liquid Discharge	
η	Pump efficiency	–
$P_{heat,AGEV}$	Mean heat power input of AGEV	kWh
$P_{el,AGEV}$	Mean electrical power input of AGEV	kWh

856

857 **Supplementary material:**

858 Appendix A

859 **Data availability:**

860 The research data are publicly available in the Zenodo repository under the following
861 doi:10.5281/zenodo.15020107.

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